

1 **Marine Traffic Noise Causes Hearing Loss and Affects Behaviour and**
2 **Reproduction in the Marine Medaka (*Oryzias melastigma*)**

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22 **Abstract**

23 Anthropogenic noise has become a pervasive pollutant in marine ecosystems, with traffic
24 noise being a major contributor. Despite increasing concerns, little is known about its
25 impact across multiple biological levels, including the auditory system, behaviour, and
26 reproduction of marine fish.

27 This study examines the effects of chronic exposure to maritime traffic noise, from boats
28 and ferries, using marine medaka (*Oryzias melastigma*), a well-established model
29 organism in marine ecotoxicology.

30 Our findings present the first demonstration of traffic noise-induced hearing loss in a
31 marine fish after only 24h of exposure. Such sensory loss was not accompanied by hair
32 cell loss, suggesting non damaging cellular dysfunction.

33 Behavioural testing showed increased total swimming distance and exploratory behaviour
34 in noise-exposed males, but not in females, indicating potential sex-specific sensitivities
35 to noise exposure. Additionally, prolonged noise exposure over 15 days impacted the
36 trend in fertilized egg production over time compared to silent control conditions. These
37 findings offer novel insights into the biological impacts of traffic noise on marine fish,
38 highlighting the urgent need for further research into both proximate and ultimate
39 responses to acoustic disturbance.

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41 **Keywords:** noise pollution, hearing thresholds, auditory evoked potentials, behavioural
42 stress, fitness

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47 **Introduction**

48 Fish represent the most diverse and abundant group of vertebrates on Earth,
49 accounting for up to one-third of global biomass and playing essential roles in ecosystem
50 functioning, biodiversity, and human economies (Bar-On et al. 2018; Flandrin et al.
51 2024). Their remarkable diversity in physiological and behavioral adaptation mechanisms
52 enables fish to support vital ecosystem services, including nutrient cycling, trophic
53 regulation, and protein supply, as well as provisioning and cultural services such as
54 fisheries and recreation ((Brown et al. 2022; Nguyen et al. 2025).

55 However, increasing anthropogenic pressures are threatening these roles (Poikane
56 et al. 2017; Dudgeon 2019; Danet et al. 2024). Marine noise pollution has emerged as a
57 growing environmental concern, drawing increasing attention from both the scientific
58 community and policymakers. (Duarte et al. 2021; White et al. 2022; Hou et al. 2025). A
59 variety of anthropogenic activities, including coastal construction, seismic exploration,
60 dredging, and industrial operations, contribute to acoustic pollution, yet marine traffic
61 remains the primary and most pervasive source of underwater noise worldwide
62 (Slabbekoorn, 2019; Duarte et al., 2021). Most noise sources generate low-frequency
63 sounds that overlap with the auditory sensitivity of marine organisms, interfering with
64 their capacity to detect biologically relevant sounds and causing diverse negative
65 physiological and behavioral effects (Erbe et al, 2019; Slabbekoorn, 2019; Kunc et al.,
66 2016).

67 In aquatic environments, sound is essential for detecting key biotic cues concerning the
68 presence of conspecifics and heterospecifics, including potential mates, prey and
69 predators (Hawkins & Popper, 2018; Popper & Hawkins, 2019; Putland et al 2019), but
70 also to obtain critical abiotic information for orientation, such as water currents,
71 turbulence, and moving substrate (e.g., Lagardere et al., 1994). A few studies have

72 reported that exposure to shipping noise can induce auditory masking (Vasconcelos et al.
73 2007; Codarin et al. 2009), and experiments using either white noise or other high-
74 intensity acoustic disturbances (e.g., seismic airguns) demonstrated noise-induced
75 hearing loss following both short and long-term exposure (Scholik and Yan, 2001; (Smith
76 et al. 2004); Popper et al., 2005; Breitzler et al., 2020; Wong et al., 2022). Nevertheless,
77 whether marine traffic noise may induce hearing loss, including temporary or permanent
78 threshold shifts, remains unknown.

79 Besides auditory effects, noise exposure can result in physiological stress and
80 behavioral disruption (Jimenez et al. 2020), depending on the intensity and characteristics
81 of the acoustic disturbance and developmental stage (He et al. 2025) Slabbekoorn et al.,
82 2010; Lara & Vasconcelos, 2021; Blom et al. 2024; Duan et al. 2025). For instance,
83 behavior, growth, and development of larval Atlantic cod (*Gadus morhua*) can be affected
84 by regular exposure to both consistent and random noise. However, consistent noise has
85 more pronounced negative effects, such as reduced growth, faster utilization of yolk sacs,
86 and increased vulnerability to predators (Nedelec et al, 2015). There is still limited
87 understanding of how marine traffic noise affects reproduction and egg survival in
88 different species. However, several studies have revealed some consistent patterns. For
89 instance, research on coral reef damselfishes (*Amphiprion melanopus* and
90 *Acanthochromis polyacanthus*) shows that exposure to boat noise increases heart rates in
91 their embryos, indicating stress. Despite this, survival rates under laboratory conditions
92 were not significantly affected (Fakan and McCormic, 2019).

93 In the case of the Lusitanian toadfish (*Halobatrachus didactylus*), boat noise exposure
94 resulted in reduced levels of energy metabolism-related biomarkers in embryos, along
95 with heightened stress responses in larvae, including increased levels of superoxide
96 dismutase (SOD) and DNA damage (Faria et al., 2022). Additionally, meagre larvae

97 (*Argyrosomus regius*) exposed to boat noise showed increased consumption of lipid
98 droplets and decreased body depth, although their survival rates were not conclusively
99 impacted, suggesting potential long-term developmental effects (Trabulo et al., 2023).
100 In the Mediterranean Sea, boat noise negatively influenced the density of juvenile sparids
101 (*Diplodus sargus*, *D. puntazzo*, *D. vulgaris*), particularly affecting early post-settlers, who
102 exhibited a strong negative relationship with noise levels (Di Franco et al., 2023). This
103 indicates that noise pollution can alter recruitment patterns and may impact population
104 dynamics. Many fish species rely on sound for mating calls and courtship behaviors. For
105 example, studies on the plainfin midshipman fish showed that exposure to noise led to a
106 reduction in vocalizations, which are essential for attracting mates. Males produced fewer
107 calls and altered their vocal patterns in response to increased noise, potentially affecting
108 their reproductive success (Brown et al., 2021; Ogurek et al., 2024). Additionally, in
109 gobies, higher noise levels resulted in males diminishing their courtship calls, while
110 females were less likely to spawn in noisy environments, indicating that noise pollution
111 can disrupt reproductive interactions (De Jong et al., 2016).

112

113 To address this gap, we used the marine medaka (*Oryzias melastigma*,
114 Beloniformes), a well-established model organism in marine ecotoxicology (Chen et al.,
115 2011; Bo et al., 2011). This marine species is particularly suited for experimental research
116 due to its short generation time, transparent embryos, ease of culture, and fully sequenced
117 genome (Bever & Fekete, 2002; Kirchmaier et al., 2016; Kim et al., 2016; Bhandari, 2016;
118 Kim et al., 2018). Moreover, *O. melastigma* is geographically distributed in Asian
119 estuarine and coastal areas, particularly in the northern margin of the South China Sea
120 (Kim et al., 2018), being directly exposed to ecologically relevant stressors such as marine
121 traffic and climate change.

122 In this study, we used the marine medaka *O. melastigma* to test the effect of marine
123 traffic noise (24-h of boat and ferry sounds) on the auditory system, behavioural
124 responses, and reproductive success (fertilized egg count). Using this model species
125 allows us to establish a baseline understanding of noise-exposure effects under controlled
126 conditions, thereby contributing for a deeper knowlegde for managing coastal fish
127 populations.

128

129 **Methods**

130 **Test animals**

131 The marine medaka (*O. melastigma*) were initially sourced from a laboratory-bred
132 population from the Ocean University of China (Qingdao, China), and then reared at the
133 fish facility at the Institute of Science and Environment, University of Saint Joseph
134 (Macao SAR). Animal husbandry and breeding protocols followed established methods
135 described by Murata and Kinoshita (2019) and adapted by Lebel (2024). Fish were
136 maintained in mixed-sex stock tanks (50 cm width × 30 cm length × 24 cm height)
137 containing aerated reverse-osmosis filtered artificial seawater (30 ppt). Each stock tank
138 housed up to 50 individuals, which were fed twice daily with a combination of
139 commercial dry food and live brine shrimp, and maintained at $27 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$, pH 7–8, and
140 under a 12:12 light/dark light cycle.

141 All fish used in this study were sexually mature adults, approximately 12 months old. For
142 audiometry, 8 males (26.5 ± 2.4 mm standard length, mean \pm standard deviation, 22.3-
143 31.5 mm range) and 8 females (22.8 ± 2.3 mm, 19.1-26.4 mm) were used. For inner ear
144 histological analysis, another group of 9 males (21.9 ± 2.5 mm, 19-26.85 mm) and 9
145 females (19.2 ± 1 mm, 17.0-20.2 mm) were assessed. Behavioural testing involved 22
146 males (26.4 ± 2.18 mm, 22.3-31.5 mm) and 22 females (23.1 ± 2.2 mm, 19.6-26.4 mm).

147 To assess reproductive effects, a total of 56 males (22.6 ± 1.33 mm \pm 20.8-24 range) and
148 112 females (18.44 ± 4.58 mm, 12-22.35 range) were considered.

149 All procedures followed the ethical guidelines enforced at the University of Saint Joseph
150 and approved by the Division of Animal Control and Inspection of the Civic and
151 Municipal Affairs Bureau of Macao, license AL017/DICV/SIS/2016.

152

153 **Acoustic Treatment for audiometry and behavioral assessment**

154 Fish were randomly assigned to one of two acoustic treatments, either a silent control or
155 noise exposure. Treatment tanks consisted of glass aquaria (59 cm length \times 29 cm width
156 \times 47 cm height; 70 L), housed within a custom-made soundproof chamber mounted over
157 two granite plates separated by rubber pads to minimize external vibrations (Fig.1A). A
158 total of six tanks were used for this study, which were at least 50 cm apart to minimize
159 potential acoustic contamination between treatments.

160 Acoustic treatment was delivered through underwater speakers (UW30, Electro-Voice,
161 MN, USA) mounted on one side of the tank (Fig. 1A), powered by ST-50 amplifiers (Ai
162 Shang Ke, China) and controlled via a laptop running Adobe Audition 3.0 (Adobe
163 Systems Inc., USA). Fish were exposed to acoustic treatment continuously for 24 hours,
164 with sound playback starting between 9:00 and 10:00. The acoustic playback consisted
165 of a mix of four small boat and ten ferry passages recorded in the Tagus estuary and
166 broadcasted at approximately 135 dB re 1 μ Pa (measured at the highest energy interval
167 of each boat passage) (Fig. 1A,B)– see Amorim et al (2022) for further details on sound
168 playback used. Prior to each treatment, Sound Pressure Levels (SPL) were calibrated
169 using a Brüel & Kjær 8104 hydrophone (Naerum, Denmark; sensitivity: -205 dB re
170 1 V/ μ Pa; frequency range: 0.1 Hz–120 kHz), connected to a Brüel & Kjær 2270 sound

171 level meter. Adjustments were made using the amplifier to achieve the target RMS sound
172 level (LZS: slow time, linear frequency weighting, 6.3 Hz–20 kHz) measured at the center
173 of the tank. The control tank was assembled exactly as in the acoustic treatment tank,
174 including the sound system but without sound playback.

175 For audiometry and inner ear histological analyses, fish were initially isolated for at least
176 7 days in 5 L tanks under quiet laboratory conditions, ranging between 103 to 108 dB re
177 1 μ Pa. These tanks were not equipped with filtering system to avoid additional noise but
178 were subject to frequent water changes to maintain adequate water quality. Light and
179 temperature conditions were kept similar to stock tanks. After this acclimatation, animals
180 were transferred to treatment tanks but confined within a mesh box (15 \times 15 \times 15 cm; 1
181 mm mesh) suspended at the center of the tank, which helped minimize variation in the
182 amplitude of the noise treatment (\pm 8 dB) across individuals.

183

184 **Auditory Evoked Potential Measurements**

185 For audiometry, marine medaka were lightly anaesthetised with 300 mg/L tricaine
186 methanesulfonate (MS-222, Arcos Organics, NJ, USA), buffered with double
187 concentration of sodium bicarbonate, until loss of equilibrium and opercular movements,
188 which took approximately 2-5 min (Murata et al., 2019). Subsequently, specimens were
189 securely placed on a custom-made sponge holder with a net covering the posterior part of
190 body and positioned in the test tank (dimensions?) with the head just below the water
191 surface, allowing normal breathing after recovering from anaesthesia. Speaker?

192 The entire experimental setup was on top of an anti-vibration air table (Vibraplane, KS
193 Kinetic Systems, MA, USA) placed within a walk-in soundproof booth (120a-3, IAC
194 Acoustics, North Aurora, IL, USA).

195

196 The Auditory Evoked Potential (AEP) technique was applied in accordance with
197 established methodologies (Breitzler et al., 2020; Wong et al., 2022; Ramos et al., 2025).
198 Briefly, a stainless-steel recording electrode (0.40 mm diameter, 13 mm length, Rochester
199 Electro-Medical, Inc., FL, USA) was firmly placed against the skin over the brainstem
200 region, while a similar electrode was used as reference and positioned on the side of the
201 body. AEP responses were recorded using a TDT system 3 (System 3, Tucker-Davis
202 Technologies, Alachua, FL, USA), with signals amplified (RA4LI/RA4PA), band-pass
203 filtered (0.1–1 kHz), digitized (16-bit, ± 4 mV), and processed via a Multi-I/O processor
204 (RZ6) (Fig. 2). Tone bursts (20 ms, 2 ms rise/fall) at frequencies ranging from 100 to
205 6000 Hz were generated using TDT SigGen software and presented at least 500 times per
206 frequency in alternating polarities (180° phase shift) via BioSig software. Auditory
207 thresholds were defined as the lowest amplitude eliciting a detectable AEP response in at
208 least two averaged responses, based on consistent waveform shape, latency shift, and/or
209 a spectral peak at twice the stimulus frequency (via FFT analysis). The last two criteria
210 were not always complied simultaneously in all AEP traces.

211 Audiometry was performed on both males and females on alternating days. At the end of
212 experiments, fish were recovered in individual aerated tanks containing system water
213 before being returned to stock tanks.

214

215 **Inner ear histology**

216 Inner ear saccular epithelia were obtained from selected specimens immediately
217 following noise treatments. Animals were subjected to an overdose with MS-222 (300 mg/L)
218 buffered with sodium bicarbonate. We followed previously described methods to extract
219 fish inner ear sensory epithelia and stain saccular hair cells (Wong et al 2022). Firstly,
220 fish heads were removed and fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde (Sigma, USA) at 4°C

221 overnight, and then thoroughly rinsed with PBS 3 times, for at least 5 minutes each time.
222 Saccular sensory epithelia were then dissected in PBS bath under a stereomicroscope
223 (Stemi 2000CS, Zeiss, Germany).
224 To stain the hair cells, the tissue was then rinsed 3 times for 5 min with PBS and incubated
225 in Alexa Fluor 488 phalloidin (diluted 1:1000; Invitrogen, ThermoFisher Scientific,
226 Waltham, USA) for 30 min. Finally, the samples were rinsed 3 times in PBS and whole-
227 mounted with Fluoromount-G (Southern Biotech, Birmingham, USA).
228 The tissue samples were imaged using a confocal imaging system (STELLARIS 5 LIA,
229 Leica Microsystems CMS GmbH) with Leica Application Suite X software (LAS X,
230 Leica Microsystems). Hair cell bundles were manually counted in four non-overlapping
231 $900\ \mu\text{m}^2$ regions distributed along the rostral-caudal axis of the saccule. The hair cell
232 orientation patterns were also analyzed and defined based on the direction of
233 depolarization, namely from the shortest stereocilia to the kinocilium. Although
234 phalloidin does not label the kinocilium, its position can be inferred as a dark hole at the
235 level of the cuticular plate (Chaves et al 2017).

236

237 Open Field **Behavioural Assessment**

238 To evaluate the impact of noise treatment on swimming activity and anxiety-like
239 behaviour, we adopted the Open Field Test (OFT) following the procedure described for
240 zebrafish and medaka (Sataa et al., 2020; Vasconcelos et al. 2023; Lebel et al, 2024). This
241 test evaluates exploratory behaviour by quantifying the distance travelled and the fish
242 within the arena, and also the thigmotaxis, which is the tendency to stay close to the tank
243 walls as an indicator of anxiety-like behaviour.

244 The behavioral assessment was carried out in a square clear acrylic tank (W280 x L 280
245 x H 200 mm) (Fig.1C). The arena was filled with seawater to a depth of 5 cm, and its

246 outer walls were covered with opaque white panels to minimize external visual stimuli.
247 The tank was placed inside a recording chamber on a backlit table illuminated by infrared
248 LEDs (850 nm) and white LED strips. Fish were gently transferred from the treatment
249 tank to the center of the OFT arena using a small net. Two arenas (one fish per arena)
250 were recorded simultaneously for 20 minutes using a monochrome camera (Daheng
251 MER-2000-19U3M, equipped with a Sony IMX-183 CMOS sensor, 12 mm ZLKC lens,
252 and Zomei 850 nm infrared-pass filter). The camera was mounted vertically 50 cm above
253 the arenas. Between trials, the water in the arenas was replaced to eliminate possible
254 chemical cues from previous fish.

255 Videos were analysed using EthoVision XT 15 (Noldus Information Technology,
256 Netherlands) to generate a tracking line for each individual. Specific parameters were
257 calculated based on the overall 20 min recording and 5 minutes time bins: total distance
258 traveled (cm); time spent swimming (s); freezing ratio (define); and time spent in the
259 central area (s) (when distance to the tank walls was greater than one body length)
260 following previous described for this species (Rosemberg et al., 2011; Stewart et al.,
261 2012; Ansai et al., 2016; Sataa et al., 2020; Lebel et al., 2024).

262

263 **Reproductive / Fertility Analyses**

264 To investigate long-term noise effects on reproduction, the experimental tanks (59 cm
265 length × 29 cm width × 47 cm height; 70 L) allowed the fish to freely swim for up to 16
266 days. Eight independent trials were conducted (four control and four noise treatments),
267 each including seven males and fourteen female medaka. In the noise treatment tank, SPL
268 varied by up ±10 dB re 1 µPa between the speaker and the farthest point within the tank.
269 Eggs were carefully collected daily using a fine-mesh net and examined under a
270 stereomicroscope (Stemi 2000CS, Zeiss) to assess fertilization and viability. Only eggs

271 displaying clear signs of fertilization, such as the presence of a blastodisc, were included
272 in the counts. To prevent interference with subsequent daily assessments, collected eggs
273 were transferred to separate incubation tanks.

274

275 **Statistical analysis**

276 Auditory thresholds at different frequencies were analysed with two-way repeated
277 measures General Linear Model (GLM) with contrast analysis. Treatment (control vs.
278 noise exposure) was included as a between-subject factor and the different sound
279 frequencies as repeated measures (within-subject factor).

280 The effect of acoustic treatment on hair cell count was assessed using a two-way
281 ANOVA, with treatment and epithelial region as independent factors.

282 For the OFT test, a two-way ANOVA was performed to examine the effects of treatment
283 and gender on the total behavioral response during the 20-minute test and a GLM repeated
284 measures ANOVA across different time points. While the experimental groups were
285 considered a between-subject factor, the behavioral parameters for the sequential time
286 points were the repeated measures (within-subject factor). A general linear model with
287 repeated measures (GLM-RM) was conducted to evaluate the effects of treatment, time
288 (5-minute intervals), and the interaction between treatment and time on the dependent
289 variable. When the assumption of sphericity was violated, degrees of freedom were
290 corrected using the Huynh-Feldt Epsilon. Planned post hoc pairwise comparisons were
291 performed using the least significant difference (LSD) method to assess significant
292 differences between time points or treatment groups. To examine the effects of treatment
293 on the number of days on the number of eggs laid per day, we used a two-way ANOVA.
294 An analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was performed to test whether the relationship
295 between day and egg production varied by treatment group.

296 Parametric assumptions were complied, namely data were normally distributed and
297 variances were homogeneous. The statistical analysis was performed with IBM SPSS v26
298 (IBM Corp. Armonk, USA).

299

300 **Results**

301 **Noise-Induced Hearing Loss**

302 The marine medaka exhibited an overall auditory sensitivity bandwidth of 100-6000 Hz.
303 The auditory thresholds were consistently the lowest at 400 Hz (110.6 ± 7.5 dB, mean \pm
304 standard deviation; 102.5-125 dB range) and the highest at 4000 Hz (138.7 ± 2.3 dB; 135-
305 140 range). Since auditory responses at 4000 and 6000 Hz were not consistently present
306 in all recordings, they were excluded from statistical analysis.

307 Auditory thresholds were significantly affected by the acoustic treatment ($F_{(1,14)}=31.64$, p
308 <0.001) with control showing lower thresholds compared to noise group at 200 Hz
309 ($p=0.022$), 400 Hz ($p=0.005$), 600 Hz ($p=0.008$) and 800 Hz ($p=0.01$) (Fig. 3). Noise
310 induced threshold shifts of 12.2 ± 4.7 dB at 200 Hz, 9.4 ± 2.8 dB at 400 Hz, 6.6 ± 2.1 dB
311 at 600 Hz, and 7.2 ± 1.7 dB at 800 Hz.

312 To investigate whether the observed sensory loss could be associated to morphological
313 damage in the inner ear, the saccular epithelia were examined. Overall, no signs of tissue
314 damage were detected. In the rostral region, hair cells were organized with a lower area
315 containing rostrally oriented cells positioned in parallel opposition to an upper area with
316 caudally oriented cells (see Fig 4A,B). In the middle and caudal saccular regions, hair
317 cells were distributed in a dorsal-ventral opposing pattern (Fig 4A,B). Comparison
318 between the two treatment groups revealed no differences between control and noise
319 groups along the saccular epithelia ($F_{(3,108)}=1.918$, $p=0.131$) (Fig.4C), indicating that
320 sensitivity loss was not associated with a reduction in hair cell number.

321

322 **Behavioural assessment of acoustic stress**

323 An initial between-subjects analysis revealed no significant main effect of acoustic
324 treatment in any behavioural parameter measured (total distance travelled: $F_{(1,40)}=1.438$,
325 $p=0.238$; time spent in the center: $F_{(1,40)}=1.149$, $p=0.290$; freezing ratio: $F_{(1,40)}=0.144$,
326 $p=0.707$), gender (total distance travelled: $F_{(1,40)}=0.479$, $p=0.493$; time spent in the center:
327 $F_{(1,40)}=0.583$, $p=0.450$; freezing ratio: $F_{(1,40)}=0.008$, $p=0.928$), nor any interaction between
328 them (total distance travelled: $F_{(1,40)}=0.50$, $p=0.824$, time spent in the center: $F_{(1,40)}=0.067$,
329 $p=0.796$; freezing ratio: $F_{(1,40)}=1.819$, $p=0.184$), for any of the measured behaviors
330 averaged over the 20-minute session.

331 The swimming activity over the 20-minute period was then analyzed in separate 5-minute
332 time bins. There was a significant main effect of time on distance travelled ($F_{(2,056, 82.241)}=11.084$,
333 $p<0.001$), indicating that swimming behavior changed across the test
334 duration. However, there was no statistically difference on time \times treatment interaction
335 ($F_{(6,168, 82.241)}=1.329$, $p=0.253$), suggesting that changes over time did not differ
336 statistically between treatments. Pairwise comparisons (LSD) revealed that during the
337 first 5-minute interval, noise-exposed males travelled significantly more than control
338 males ($p=0.045$, Fig 5A). No other significant differences were observed across time
339 points between treatment groups (all $p>0.09$). For the time spent in the center, the main
340 effect of time was not statistically significant ($F_{(2,161, 86.446)}=0.848$, $p=0.439$),
341 suggesting no changes over time. However, the interaction between time and treatment
342 approached statistical significance ($F_{(6,483, 86.446)}=1.961$, $p=0.075$), suggesting a trend
343 toward differential patterns of zone occupancy across treatments. An initial between-
344 subjects analysis revealed a significant difference on the gender ($F_{(1,40)}=6.176$, $p=0.017$)
345 in the first 5 minutes, for the time spent at the center. Pairwise comparisons using **LSD**

346 revealed this significant difference between noise-exposed females and noise-exposed
347 males, with NM spending more time in the zone than NF ($p=0.004$, Fig.5B), suggesting
348 that noise exposure may differentially modulate exploratory or anxiety-like behaviors in
349 the two sexes, with males showing greater central exploration under stress.

350

351 **Long-term noise effects on reproduction**

352 Noise exposure for 15 days did not significantly affect the total number of fertilized eggs
353 compared to the control group ($(F_{(1,96)}=0.78, p=0.38; \text{Fig.6A})$). However, while egg
354 production increased over time in both groups, the rate of increase differed significantly
355 between treatments ($(F_{(1,124)}=10.86, p=0.0013; \Delta\text{AIC}=8.75)$), indicating that the effect of
356 day on egg production was significantly different between groups. Control fish exhibited
357 a consistently rising trend in daily egg production, with a mean of 7.2 eggs/day, whereas
358 the noise-exposed group showed a lower and more variable production rate, averaging
359 2.7 eggs/day (Fig. 6B).

360

361 **Discussion**

362 The present work provides the first evidence of hearing loss induced by marine traffic
363 noise in a marine fish species. Behavioural assessments showed potential sex-specific
364 sensitivities to noise exposure, with noise-exposed males exhibiting increased on
365 exploratory behavior than in noise-exposed females. Moreover, prolonged noise exposure
366 (over 15 days) impacted the reproductive output, reducing the daily trend in fertilized
367 eggs. These findings provide novel insights into the ecological consequences of
368 anthropogenic noise, highlighting its impact on marine fish across multiple functional
369 domains, including sensory, behavioral, and reproductive responses.

370

371 **Noise-Induced Hearing Loss**

372 Chronic exposure to boat noise has been shown to significantly increase auditory
373 thresholds in fish, particularly at frequencies critical for their natural environment, which
374 suggests that noise pollution can interfere with the fish's ability to perceive important
375 acoustic cues such as predator signals or social interactions. This disruption could have
376 consequences for survival and reproductive success, as elevated auditory thresholds can
377 impede the detection of vital environmental sounds (Holles et al., 2013; McCormick et
378 al., 2018).

379 Moreover, the elevated thresholds observed in noise-exposed fish align with findings in
380 other aquatic species, indicating that boat noise can degrade sensory systems, especially
381 in species that rely on particle motion detection for communication and predator
382 avoidance (McCormick et al., 2019; Nichols et al., 2015; Blom et al., 2019). For instance,
383 studies have demonstrated that anthropogenic noise can impair the auditory capabilities
384 of various fish species, leading to altered behaviors that may affect their reproductive
385 success and overall fitness (Cox et al., 2018; Simpson et al., 2016). The physiological
386 stress induced by noise exposure can further exacerbate these effects, as evidenced by
387 research showing that noise can disrupt normal physiological processes in fish, leading
388 to reduced reproductive output and impaired behavioral responses (Nedelec et al., 2015;
389 Maxwell et al., 2018).

390 The implications of these findings extend beyond individual species, contributing to a
391 growing body of literature on noise pollution's impact on marine ecosystems. The
392 disruption of auditory functions and subsequent behavioral changes can alter predator-
393 prey dynamics and social structures within fish populations, potentially leading to broader
394 ecological consequences (Purser & Radford, 2011; Richter et al., 2014). As such,

395 understanding the effects of chronic noise exposure is crucial for the conservation of
396 marine biodiversity and the management of aquatic environments, particularly in areas
397 heavily trafficked by boats (Filby et al., 2012; Barcelo-Serra et al., 2021).

398 **Behavioural Evidence of Acoustic Disturbance**

399 In line with previous studies in medaka and other small teleosts, our findings highlight
400 that exploratory behaviors—such as increased locomotor activity and time spent in the
401 central zone of the open field—are modulated by the nature of external cues and vary
402 across sexes. Specifically, exposure to acoustic stimuli evoked distinct behavioral
403 trajectories in male and female *Oryzias melastigma*, particularly during the initial five
404 minutes of observation. Males exposed to noise displayed heightened locomotion and
405 increased center-zone exploration, while noise-exposed females were less exploratory
406 and initially restricted to peripheral zones. These sex-specific patterns evolved over time:
407 male exploratory behavior diminished while females gradually increased their central
408 activity, suggesting differential coping styles and temporal adaptation to environmental
409 novelty.

410 These behavioral trajectories align with evidence of sexually dimorphic stress responses
411 in medaka. For instance, López-Olmeda et al. (2021) demonstrated that long photoperiods
412 impaired learning performance primarily in males, revealing heightened male sensitivity
413 to environmental stressors and Lucon-Xiccato et al.(2022) that photoperiod altered brain
414 lateralisation, inhibitory control, and learning. Our findings suggest that males may
415 initially adopt an arousal-driven response to novelty, whereas females exhibit more
416 conservative strategies that change with exposure duration. Such divergence may be
417 attributed to hormonal modulation: oxytocin signaling has been implicated in sex-specific
418 mating preferences behavior in medaka (Yokoi et al., 2016; 2020), and could also underlie
419 differential responses to sensory stimuli.

420 Exploratory behavior in our experiment was also shaped by the integration of
421 multisensory cues. Fish that explored the central area more frequently also tended to
422 travel greater distances, a behavioral profile previously associated with boldness (Sataa
423 et al., 2020; Lucon-Xiccato et al., 2022). Similar trends have been documented in both
424 zebrafish and medaka exposed to anxiolytic agents such as fluoxetine, which increased
425 center-zone occupancy (Winberg & Thörnqvist, 2016; Ansai et al., 2016). Moreover,
426 olfactory cues associated with social stimuli can mitigate stress and promote exploration,
427 as observed in zebrafish (Santacà et al., 2019), and our results suggest that the perception
428 and processing of such cues may be sex-dependent under noisy or novel conditions.

429 These observations are reinforced by recent work from Lebel et al. (2024), who
430 demonstrated that chemical cues from conspecifics reduce thigmotaxis and enhance
431 exploratory behavior in marine medaka, particularly when combined with visual cues.
432 Their findings support the notion that multisensory integration—rather than unimodal cue
433 detection—is critical for appropriate behavioral modulation in social and stressful
434 contexts. Nakayasu and Watanabe (2013) showed that medaka respond robustly to visual
435 biological motion, even in the absence of morphological or olfactory features,
436 emphasizing that the type of cue and its ecological relevance shape behavioral output.

437 Taken together, our results point to a complex, sex-specific behavioral plasticity in
438 response to novel or stressful stimuli in marine medaka. Males and females appear to
439 differentially prioritize and process sensory information, likely reflecting evolutionary
440 pressures shaping social behavior and environmental responsiveness. This highlights the
441 importance of considering both sex and sensory context in behavioral ecotoxicology
442 studies, especially under increasing anthropogenic disturbances such as acoustic
443 pollution, which may disproportionately disrupt sensory integration and stress coping
444 mechanisms in aquatic species.

445

446 **Noise Effects on Reproduction**

447 Reproductive data from the study initially indicated a boost in egg production
448 among noise-exposed fish; however, this increase was not sustained, with reproductive
449 output returning to baseline levels after prolonged exposure. This pattern suggests a short-
450 term adaptive response to stress, where reproductive investment may increase under
451 perceived threats, as supported by research indicating that stress can temporarily enhance
452 reproductive efforts in various species (Zhang et al., 2022). However, the inability to
453 maintain this elevated output implies that prolonged exposure to noise imposes
454 physiological costs that can overcome compensatory mechanisms, a concept in the
455 literature regarding stress-induced reproductive boosts being often temporary and
456 potentially leading to exhaustion or reduced fitness over time (Neo et al., 2015; Simpson
457 et al., 2016).

458 Auditory deficits in fish exposed to chronic noise likely contribute to heightened stress
459 levels, leading to altered behaviors and an initial enhancement of reproductive effort that
460 finally declines. The increased activity levels observed in noise-exposed males suggest
461 that these fish may be allocating more energy to coping mechanisms in response to stress,
462 which could divert resources away from reproduction and other vital processes. This
463 aligns with findings who noted that stress induced by noise can disrupt cognitive behavior
464 and focus, further supporting the notion that noise exposure can impose multi-level stress
465 on marine organisms (Kusku et al. 2019).

466 Additionally, a meta-analysis that highlights the widespread effects of aquatic noise on
467 fish behavior and physiology, indicating that such stressors can lead to significant
468 alterations in energy allocation and reproductive strategies (Cox et al., 2018). The initial
469 boost in reproductive output among noise-exposed fish may reflect a short-term adaptive

470 response to perceived threats, and stress responses can temporarily enhance reproductive
471 efforts in certain species (Zhang et al., 2022). For instance, studies have shown that fish
472 exposed to boat noise exhibit altered territorial behaviors and reduced success in repelling
473 intruders, indicating that noise can disrupt critical ecological functions (McCormick et
474 al., 2018; Sebastianutto et al., 2011). Furthermore, the link between anthropogenic noise
475 and changes in risk assessment behaviors in fish, can have effects on population dynamics
476 and sustainability (McCormick et al., 2019).

477 These findings illustrate the complex interplay between sensory impairment, behavior,
478 and reproduction in response to noise pollution. The evidence suggests that while initial
479 responses to stressors may be adaptive, the long-term consequences of chronic noise
480 exposure can lead to detrimental effects on both behavior and reproductive success. This
481 aligns with the broader understanding of how anthropogenic noise impacts aquatic life,
482 emphasizing the need for further research to explore these dynamics in natural
483 environments (Bignami et al., 2013).

484 In conclusion, the evidence presented shows the significant impacts of chronic boat
485 noise on marine medaka, highlighting the connection of auditory, behavioral, and
486 reproductive systems in the face of environmental stressors. This study not only adds to
487 the existing literature on noise pollution but also calls for further research to explore the
488 long-term consequences of such disturbances on aquatic life and ecosystems.

489

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494 **Competing Interests**

495 The authors declare there are no competing interests.

496

497 **Supplemental Information**

498 Supplemental data (AEP values) can be found at supplementary materials.

499

500 **References**

501 Adamek-Urbańska D, Błażewicz E, Sobień M, Kasprzak R, Kamaszewski M.
502 2021. Histological study of suprabranchial chamber membranes in Anabantoidei and
503 Clariidae fishes. *Animals*, 11:1158. DOI: 10.3390/ani11041158.

504 Alton LA, Portugal S, White, CR. 2013. Balancing the competing requirements
505 of air-breathing and display behaviour during male-male interactions in Siamese fighting
506 fish *Betta splendens*. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology – A* 164:363–367
507 DOI:10.1016/j.cbpa.2012.11.012.

508 Amorim MCP. 2006. Diversity of sound production in fish. In: Ladich F, Collin
509 SP, Moller P, Kapoor BG, eds. *Communication in fishes*. vol 1. Enfield: Science
510 Publishers, 71-105.

511 Amoser S, Ladich F. 2005. Are hearing sensitivities of freshwater fish adapted to
512 the ambient noise in their habitats? *Journal of Experimental Biology* 208:3533–3542
513 DOI:10.1242/jeb.01809.

514 Amoser S, Ladich F. 2010. Year-round variability of ambient noise in temperate
515 freshwater habitats and its implications for fishes. *Aquatic Sciences* 72:371–378 DOI:
516 10.1007/s00027-010-0136-9.

517 Anderson KA, Rountree RA, Juanes F. 2008. Soniferous fishes in the Hudson
518 river. *Transactions of the American Fisheries Society* 137:616–626 DOI: 10.1577/T05-
519 220.1.

520 Belmar O, Booker D, Álvarez-Cabria M, Peñas FJ, Barquín J. 2019. Modelling
521 physical characteristics of river habitats. *River Research and Applications* 35:804–817
522 DOI: 10.1002/rra.3456.

523 Breitzler L, Lau IH, Fonseca PJ, Vasconcelos RO. 2020. Noise-induced hearing
524 loss in zebrafish: investigating structural and functional inner ear damage and recovery.
525 *Hearing Research* 391:107952 DOI:10.1016/j.heares.2020.107952.

526 Castro N, Ros AFH, Becker K, Oliveira, RF. 2006. Metabolic costs of
527 aggressive behaviour in the Siamese fighting fish, *Betta splendens*. *Aggressive*
528 *Behavior*, 32:474-480 DOI: 10.1002/ab.20147.

529 Cerezer FO, Dambros CS, Coelho MTP, Cassemiro FAS, Barreto E, Albert JS,
530 Wuest RO, Graham CH. 2023. Accelerated body size evolution in upland environments
531 is correlated with recent speciation in South American freshwater fishes. *Nature*
532 *Communications* 14:6070 DOI: 10.1038/s41467-023-41812-7.

533 Decker E, Parker B, Linke S, Capon S, Sheldon F. 2020. Singing streams:
534 Describing freshwater soundscapes with the help of acoustic indices. *Ecology and*
535 *Evolution* 10:4979-4989 DOI: 10.1002/ece3.6251.

536 Desjonquères C, Rybak F, Depraetere M, Gasc A, Le Viol I, Pavoine S, Sueur J.
537 2015. First description of underwater acoustic diversity in three temperate ponds. *PeerJ*
538 DOI: 10.7717/peerj.1393.

539 Desjonquères C, Rybak F, Ulloa JS, Kempf A, Hen AB, Sueur J. 2020.
540 Monitoring the acoustic activity of an aquatic insect population in relation to
541 temperature, vegetation, and noise. *Freshwater Biology* 65:107–116
542 DOI:10.1111/fwb.13171.

543 Dudgeon D, Arthington AH, Gessner MO, Kawabata ZI, Knowler DJ, Lévêque
544 C, Naiman RJ, Prieur-Richard AH, Soto D, Stiassny MLJ. 2006. Freshwater
545 biodiversity: importance, threats, status and conservation challenges. *Biological*
546 *Reviews* 81:163-182 DOI: 10.1017/S1464793105006950.

547 Fan G, Chan J, Ma K, Yang B, Zhang H, Shi C, Lae H, Ren Z, Xu Q, Wang J,
548 Chen W, Shao L, Gonçalves D, Ramos A, Cardoso SD, Guo M, Cai J, Xu X, Wang J,
549 Yang H, Liu X, Wang Y. 2018. Chromosome-level reference genome of the siamese
550 fighting fish *Betta splendens*, a model species for the study of aggression. *Gigascience* 7
551 DOI: 10.1093/gigascience/giy087.

552 Fay R. 2009. Soundscapes and the sense of hearing of fishes. *Integrative*
553 *Zoology* 4:26–32 DOI: 10.1111/j.1749-4877.2008.00132.x.

554 Greenhalgh JA, Genner MJ, & Jones G. 2023. Diel variation in insect-dominated
555 temperate pond soundscapes and guidelines for survey design. *Freshwater Biology* 68:
556 1148-1160 DOI: 10.1111/fwb.14092.

557 Gozlan RE, Karimov BK, Zadereev E, Kuznetsova D, Brucet S. 2019. Status,
558 trends, and future dynamics of freshwater ecosystems in Europe and Central Asia.
559 *Inland Waters* 9:78-94 DOI:10.1080/20442041.2018.1510271.

560 Hawkins AD. 1981. The hearing abilities of fish. In: Tavolga WN, Popper AN,
561 Fay RR. *Hearing and Sound Communication in Fishes*. New York: Springer, 109-133.

562 Hawkins AD, Popper AN. 2018. Directional hearing and sound source
563 localization by fishes. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* 144:3329–3350
564 DOI:10.1121/1.5082306.

565 Hui TH, Ng PK. 2005. The fighting fishes (Teleostei: Osphronemidae: genus
566 *Betta*) of Singapore, Malaysia and Brunei. *The Raffles Bulletin of Zoology* 13:43-99.

567 Jaroensutansinee M, Jaroensutansinee K. 2005. Bubble nest habitat
568 characteristics of wild Siamese fighting fish. *Journal of Fish Biology* 58:1311-1319
569 DOI: 10.1111/j.1095-8649.2001.tb02288.x.

570 Kowasupat C, Panijpan B, Ruenwongsa P. 2012. *Betta siamorientalis*, a new
571 species of bubble-nest building fighting fish (Teleostei: Osphronemidae) from eastern
572 Thailand. *Vertebrate Zoology* 62:387-397 DOI: 10.3897/vz.62.e31398.

573 Kwon Y, Vranken N, Hoge C, Lichak M, Norovich A, Francis K, Camacho-
574 Garcia J, Bista I, Wood J, Mccarthy S, Chow W, Tan HH, Howe K, Bandara S, Lintig
575 JV, Ruber L, Durbin R, Svardal H, Bendesky A. 2022. Genomic consequences of
576 domestication of the Siamese fighting fish. *Science Advances* 8
577 DOI: 10.1126/sciadv.abm4950.

578 Ladich F, Yan HY. 1998. Correlation between auditory sensitivity and
579 vocalization in anabantoid fishes. *Journal of Comparative Physiology A*, 182:737-746
580 DOI: 10.1007/s003590050218.

581 Ladich F. 2000. Acoustic communication and the evolution of hearing in fishes.
582 *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 355:1285-8
583 DOI: 10.1098/rstb.2000.0685.

584 Ladich F, Popper AN. 2001. Comparison of the inner ear ultrastructure between
585 teleost fishes using different channels for communication. *Hearing Research*, 154:62-72
586 DOI: 10.1016/S0378-5955(01)00217-9.

587 Ladich F, Popper AN. 2004. Parallel evolution in fish hearing organs. In:
588 Manley G, Fay RR, Popper AN, ed. *Evolution of the Vertebrate Auditory System*. New
589 York: Springer-Verlag 95–127.

590 Ladich F. 2007. Females whisper briefly during sex: context- and sex-specific
591 differences in sounds made by croaking gouramis. *Animal Behaviour*, 73:379-387
592 DOI:10.1016/j.anbehav.2006.04.014.

593 Ladich F, Fay RR. 2013. Auditory evoked potential audiometry in fish. *Reviews*
594 *in Fish Biology and Fisheries*, 23:317-364 DOI: 10.1007/s11160-012-9297-z.

595 Ladich F, Schulz-Mirbach T. 2016. Diversity in fish auditory systems: one of the
596 riddles of sensory biology. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution*, 4
597 DOI:10.3389/fevo.2016.00028.

598 Lagardere JP, Begout ML, Lafaye JY, Villotte JP. 1994. Influence of wind-
599 produced noise on orientation in the Sole (*Solea solea*). *Canadian Journal of Fisheries*
600 *and Aquatic Sciences* 51:1258–1264 DOI: 10.1139/f94-125.

601 Lara RA, Vasconcelos RO. 2019. Characterization of the natural soundscape of
602 zebrafish and comparison with the captive noise conditions. *Zebrafish* 16:152-164 DOI:
603 10.1089/zeb.2018.1654.

604 Lichak MR, Barber JR, Kwon YM, Francis KX, Bendesky A. 2022. Care and
605 use of Siamese Fighting Fish (*Betta Splendens*) for research. *Comparative Medicine*
606 72:169-180 DOI: 10.30802/AALAS-CM-22-000051.

607 Lugli, M. 2010. Sounds of shallow water fishes pitch within the quiet window of
608 the habitat ambient noise. *Journal of Comparative Physiology A* 196:439-451 DOI:
609 /10.1007/s00359-010-0528-.

610 Maruska KP, Sisneros, JA. 2015. Sex steroid-dependent modulation of acoustic
611 communication systems in fishes. In: Ladich F, ed. *Sound Communication in Fishes*.
612 Vienna: Springer DOI:10.1007/978-3-7091-1846-7_7.

613 Manel S, Guerin PE, Mouillot D, Blanchet S, Velez L, Albouy C, Pellissier L.
614 2020. Global determinants of freshwater and marine fish genetic diversity. *Nature*
615 *Communications* 11:692 DOI: 10.1038/s41467-020-14409-7.

616 Maruska KP, Sisneros JA. 2016. Comparison of electrophysiological auditory
617 measures in fishes. *Advances in Experimental Medicine and Biology* 877:227-254 DOI:
618 10.1007/978-3-319-21059-9_11.

619 Montie EW, Vega S, Powell M. 2015. Seasonal and spatial patterns of fish
620 sound production in the May River, South Carolina. *Transactions of the American*
621 *Fisheries Society* 144:705–716 DOI: 10.1080/00028487.2015.1037014.

622 Nakatani M, Miya M, Mabuchi K, Saitoh K, Nishida M. 2011. Evolutionary
623 history of Otophysi (Teleostei), a major clade of the modern freshwater fishes:
624 Pangaeon origin and Mesozoic radiation. *BMC Evolutionary Biology* 11:177 DOI:
625 10.1186/1471-2148-11-177.

626 Nelson JS, Grande TC, Wilson MVH. 2016. *Fishes of the World, Fifth Edition*.
627 Hoboken, New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons, Inc. DOI: [10.1002/9781119174844](https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119174844).

628 Nur FM, Batubara AS, Fadli N, Rizal S, Siti-Azizah MN, Muchlisin ZA. 2022.
629 Diversity, distribution, and conservation status of *Betta* fish (Teleostei: Osphronemidae)

630 in Aceh Waters, Indonesia. *The European Zoological Journal* 89:142-151. DOI:
631 10.1080/24750263.2022.2029587.

632 Palmiotti A, Lichak M, Shih P, Bendesky A. 2023. Genetic manipulation of
633 *Betta* fish. *Frontiers in Genome* 5 DIO: 10.1101/2023.02.16.528733.

634 Panijpan B, Sriwattanarothai N, Kowasupat C, Ruenwongsa P, Jeenthong T,
635 Phumchoosri A. 2017. Biodiversity of bubble-nest building and mouth-brooding
636 fighting fish species of the genus *Betta* in Southeast Asia. *The Thailand Natural History*
637 *Museum Journal* 11: 1–21.

638 Picado A, Mendes J, Ruela R, Pinheiro J, Dias JM. 2020. Physico-chemical
639 characterization of two Portuguese coastal systems: Ria de Alvor and Mira Estuary.
640 *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering* 8:537 DOI: 10.3390/jmse8070537.

641 Pomoim N, Hughes AC, Trisurat Y, Corlett RT. 2022. Vulnerability to climate
642 change of species in protected areas in Thailand. *Scientific Reports* 12:5705 DOI:
643 10.1038/s41598-022-09767-9.

644 Popper AN, Hawkins AD. 2019. An overview of fish bioacoustics and the
645 impacts of anthropogenic sounds on fishes. *Journal of Fish Biology* 94:692-713 DOI:
646 10.1111/jfb.13948.

647 Popper AN, Hawkins, AD. 2021. Fish hearing and how it is best determined.
648 *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 78:2325-2336 DOI: 10.1093/icesjms/fsab115

649 Putland RL, Montgomery JC, Radford CA. 2019. Ecology of fish hearing.
650 *Journal of Fish Biology* 95:39-52 DOI: 10.1111/jfb.13867.

651 Ramos A, Gonçalves D. 2019. Artificial selection for male winners in the
652 Siamese fighting fish, *Betta splendens*, correlates with high female aggression.
653 *Frontiers in Zoology* 16:34 DOI: 10.1186/s12983-019-0333-x.

654 Ramos A, Gonçalves D. 2022. Selection for winners impacts the endocrine
655 system in the Siamese fighting fish. *General and Comparative Endocrinology*
656 318:113988 DOI: 10.1016/j.ygcen.2022.113988.

657 Ramos A, Gonçalves D., Vasconcelos, RO. 2024. Exploring tropical freshwater
658 soundscapes in Southeast Asia: insights into auditory sensory adaptation of wild
659 Siamese fighting fish *Betta splendens*. bioRxiv 607752 DOI:
660 10.1101/2024.08.13.607752.

661 Rountree RA, Juanes F, Bolgan M. 2020. Temperate freshwater soundscapes: A
662 cacophony of undescribed biological sounds now threatened by anthropogenic noise.
663 *Plos One* 15 DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0221842.

664 Saidel WM, Popper AN. 1987. Sound reception in two anabantid fishes.
665 *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology A* 88:37-44 DOI: 10.1016/0300-
666 9629(87)90095-8.

667 Schneider, H. 1942. Die Bedeutung der Atemhöhle der Labyrinthfische für ihr
668 Hörvermögen. *Zeitschrift für vergleichende Physiologie* 29, 172-194 DOI:
669 10.1007/BF00304447.

670 Su H, Feng Y, Chen J, Chen J, Ma S, Fang J, Xie P. 2021. Determinants of
671 trophic cascade strength in freshwater ecosystems: a global analysis. *Ecology* 102 DOI:
672 10.1002/ecy.3370.

673 Tate M, McGoran RE, White CR, Portugal SJ. 2017. Life in a bubble: the role of
674 the labyrinth organ in determining territory, mating and aggressive behaviours in
675 anabantoids. *Journal of Fish Biology*, 9:723-749 DOI/10.1111/jfb.13357.

676 Thomson JR, Taylor MP, Fryirs KA, Brierley GJ. 2001. A geomorphological
677 framework for river characterization and habitat assessment. *Aquatic Conservation:
678 Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 11:373-389 DOI: 10.1002/aqc.467.

679 Tonolla D, Acuña V, Lorang MS, Heutschi K, Tockner K. 2010. A field-based
680 investigation to examine underwater soundscapes of five common river habitats.
681 *Hydrological Processes* 24:3146–3156 DOI: 10.1002/hyp.7730.

682 Tonolla D, Lorang MS, Heutschi K, Gotschalk CC, Tockner K. 2011.
683 Characterization of spatial heterogeneity in underwater soundscapes at the river segment
684 scale. *Limnology and Oceanography* 56:2319–2333 DOI:10.4319/lo.2011.56.6.2319.

685 Tudor M, Lopez-Anido RN, Yocius CA, Conlin SM, Hamlin HJ. 2019.
686 Ecologically relevant arsenic exposure alters female mate preference and anxiety-like
687 behavior in betta splendens. *Heliyon*, 5. DOI: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2019.e02646.

688 Veith J, Chaigne T, Svanidze A, Dressler LE, Hoffman M, Gerhardt B,
689 Judkewitz B. 2024. The mechanism for directional hearing in fish. *Nature*. 631:118-
690 124. DOI: 10.1038/s41586-024-07507.

691 Villéger S, Brosse S, Mouchet M, Mouillot D, Vanni MJ. 2017. Functional
692 ecology of fish: current approaches and future challenges. *Aquatic Science* 79:783-801
693 DOI: 10.1007/s00027-017-0546-z.

694 Yan HY. 1998. Auditory role of the suprabranchial chamber in gourami fish.
695 *Journal of Comparative Physiology A*. 183:325-33 DOI: 10.1007/s003590050259.

696 Wysocki LE, Ladich F. 2001. The ontogenetic development of auditory
697 sensitivity, vocalization and acoustic communication in the labyrinth fish *Trichopsis*
698 *vittata*. *Journal of Comparative Physiology A*, 187:177-187 DOI:
699 10.1007/s003590100186.

700 Wysocki LE, Amoser S, Ladich F. 2007. Diversity in ambient noise in European
701 freshwater habitats: noise levels, spectral profiles, and impact on fishes. *Journal of the*
702 *Acoustical Society of America* 121: 2559–2566 DOI: 10.1121/1.2713661.

703 Wong MI, Lau IH, Gordillo-Martinez F, Vasconcelos RO. 2022. The effect of
704 time regime in noise exposure on the auditory system and behavioural stress in the
705 zebrafish. *Scientific Reports* 12:15353 DOI: 10.1038/s41598-022-19573-y.

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707 **Cations and Images**

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Figure 1. Adapted from Vasconcelos et al., 2023. Experimental design showing the acoustic treatment followed by behavioural assays. **A)** After a period of isolation in silent laboratory conditions for 7 days, individuals of marine medaka (*Oryzias melastigma*) were transferred to treatment tanks for a 24-hour acclimation period and subsequently exposed shipping noise (135 dB re 1 μPa) for 24 hours. The acoustic playback consisted of a mix of four small boat and ten ferry passages recorded in the Tagus estuary and broadcasted at approximately 135 dB re 1 μPa (measured at the highest energy period of each boat passage). During this exposure, they were housed inside a mesh box (dimensions: 15 x 15 x 15 cm, 1 mm mesh) suspended 2 cm from the speaker, underwater. **B)** Power Sound Spectrum (PSD) of the sound playback used for acoustic treatment (FFT 16384 Blackmann-Harris, mean ± 95% IC). **C)** Open field test setup adapted from Lebel et al.2024. Individual males and females marine medaka were transferred from the treatment tank to the OFT tank with a small net and placed at the center of the tank. Replicates with two arenas (1 fish each) were simultaneously recorded for 20 min.

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Figure 2. **A)** Representative Auditory Evoked Potential (AEP) response curves of marine medaka (*Oryzias melastigma*) at 600 Hz under two conditions: control treatment and after 24 hours of exposure to shipping noise (135 dB re 1 μ PA). Auditory thresholds (indicated in yellow) were determined as the lowest amplitude at which a consistent response pattern was observed. Voltage scales were adjusted to optimize visibility, corresponding to the AEP curves displayed. **B)** Schematic image of the AEPs recording using a TDT system, with signals amplified (RA4LI/RA4PA), band-pass filtered (0.1–1 kHz), digitized (16-bit, ± 4 mV), and processed via a Multi-I/O processor (RZ6).

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Figure 3. Mean auditory thresholds (\pm standard error of the mean or SEM) of control (dashed grey line) and noise-exposed (continuous red line) marine medaka ($F_{(1,14)}=31.64$, $p<0.001$ poshoc tests * $p<0.05$; ** $p<0.01$). Data presented is based consisting of similar-sized individuals – 8 males and 8 females.

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Figure 4. A) Representative images showing phalloidin-stained hair cells (green) showing the four regions defined for hair cell bundle quantification in marine medaka saccular epithelia. A, anterior; D, dorsal. B) Orientation map of the hair cells bundles. Line drawing corresponds to the general shape of a typical saccular epithelia. Arrows indicate the depolarizing direction of hair bundles in a specific region. C) Comparison of hair number along the saccular epithelia along the anterior-posterior axis regions defined for hair cell bundle quantification for control and noise-exposed fish group ($F_{(3,108)}=1.918$, $p=0.131$) (mean \pm standard error of the mean).

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808 **Figure 5.** Comparison of the distance travelled during the Open Field Test (OFT). No
809 overall differences were observed among the groups for all variables measured during the
810 20 minutes. However, at specific time points within the 5-minute test, A) significant
811 differences were found among males, with noise-exposed males showing greater
812 distances travelled ($p=0.045$), and B) males exposed to noise showed higher exploratory
813 behaviors than the females of the same treatment ($p=0.004$).

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Figure 6. Daily egg production over a 15-day. **A)** No statistically significant differences were detected between groups (ANOVA: $(F_{(1,96)}=0.78, p=0.38)$), nor on any individual day. ANCOVA indicates that the effect of day on egg production was significantly different between groups ($(F_{(1, 124)}=10.86, p=0.0013; \Delta AIC=8.75)$). **B)** Comparison of individual egg production slopes (daily rate of change) for each fish, did not reach statistical significance (t-test: $p = 0.076$).